

RISK FACTORS IN RELATIVE ATTITUDE TO CHILDREN

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Abstract: In this article, child abuse is defined as physical abuse, sexual abuse, neglect, psychological abuse, and other actions aimed at achieving an inhuman goal, causing pain to a child, harming his or her health and damage to development.

Keywords: oppression, harm, exploitation, negligence, direct oppression, indirect oppression, physical violence, sexual violence

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INTRODUCTION

Today, the words "cruelty" and "maltreatment" are used as synonyms in the literature. The concept of "child abuse" (see Child Abuse) is based on the following definition proposed by the World Health Organization in 1999: " or "child abuse" "...all kinds of physical and/or emotional negative treatment, sexual oppression, careless or indifference, commercial or other exploitation".

Therefore, the term "child abuse" adopted in international practice includes the concepts of "neglect" and "neglect".

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

In Uzbekistan, the concept of "cruel and careless treatment of children" is primarily based on a legal basis. According to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, tyranny does not mean careless and indifferent attitude. Cruelty and indifference are defined as follows: Cruelty to a child is physical, sexual and psychological influence that violates the child's right to privacy, against the child's will or by taking advantage of the child's need for help. According to this definition, physical, sexual and mental forms of oppression are distinguished.

Indifference to a child - by parents or their substitutes, as well as by other persons on providing children with care, education, healthy living conditions, full education, etc. non-fulfilment or inadequate fulfillment of their obligations.

Unworthy attitudes towards children:

Physical abuse is cruelty and other actions aimed at a purpose that is not compatible with humanity, causing pain to a child and harming his health and development:

- ✓ any physical injury or pain inflicted on the child (hitting, pinching, biting, burning, choking or drowning the child)
- ✓ not to resist physical injury to the child
- ✓ physically punishing the child in any way - slapping, beating, humiliating
- ✓ child poisoning with the help of diuretics or other chemical agents
- ✓ Sexual abuse - using children to satisfy the sexual needs of adults.

Using threats, force, trickery, or confidence to lure a child into sexual activity.

- ✓ any sexual relations with the child (with or without abuse)
- ✓ any behavior that attracts a child to sex
- ✓ engaging in any sexual activities - games, conversations, photo and video images
- ✓ sexual exploitation - selling a child for sexual purposes, using pornographic photos and videos
- ✓ attraction to prostitution

Emotional (spiritual) abuse - neglecting a child, not caring, not supporting, not showing emotional closeness. The child constantly feels a lack of attention and affection, is threatened and humiliated, and this leads to increased lack of self-worth and self-confidence, including:

- ✓ lies, threats, intimidation, discrimination, insults, swearing;
- ✓ abandonment of the child, isolation
- ✓ attraction and coercion to antisocial activities
- ✓ Unreasonable demand to do things that the child cannot do
- ✓ excessive patronage that hinders the normal development of the child
- ✓ failure of adults to fulfill their obligations, violation of children's sense of trust.

Careless attitude (indifference) - non-fulfillment of vital needs that negatively affects the physical, mental, mental and social development of the child:

- ✓ neglecting, neglecting, endangering;
- ✓ indifference to the needs of the child (failure to meet the needs of food, medical care, education, communication, developmental needs);
- ✓ lack of emotional intimacy (withdrawal)
- ✓ inability (unwillingness) to protect against an existing threat

Exploitation - using a child for one's own benefit - hard labor, sexual exploitation, trafficking (taking away children for the purpose of exploitation, sale).

They distinguish four types of child abuse:

- ✓ Cruel physical relationship
- ✓ Sexual violence
- ✓ Neglect of the child's needs

✓ Psychological violence

Physical abuse is any non-accidental injury to a child.

Child sexual abuse is the use of a child or adolescent for personal sexual pleasure.

Child neglect is the chronic inability of a parent or caregiver to provide for the basic needs of a child under the age of 18.

Psychological violence, in turn, can be of two types:

✓ psychological neglect is the inability of parents or caregivers to provide the child with the necessary support, attention, psychological protection, lack of love for him.

✓ psychological cruelty - a chronic act committed by adults with the purpose of humiliating, humiliating, humiliating, teasing a child.

At first, the cause of child abuse was considered to be the psychological deviation of parents, then the focus was shifted to the social context, from which the conclusion is made that the risk factor is hidden in the value system and social isolation of parents, which condition the child's violent attitude. Later, violence was interpreted as a broken interactional social model of parent-child relations.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is necessary to say that the researchers identify the danger at the level of family and society and prove that their interaction leads to violence against children. Also, they emphasize that the existence of this or that issue does not mean the prevention of violence, but rather the possibility of its occurrence. In this case, the presence of several positive factors (social skills, positive identification of "I", etc.) reduces the impact of the risk factor.

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